

“Documentation for Application Process”

**DELIVERABLE
D3.1**

**Version 2.1
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SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. Its aim is to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until project end, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

Deliverable D3.1 – Documentation for Application Process represents a collection of documents assisting the INDUSAC co-creation application process, and will either be part of, or uploaded to, the INDUSAC platform. Templates are subject to upgrades based on feedback from end users, i.e. companies and co-creation teams.

Keywords: INDUSAC, academia-industry cooperation, methodology, co-creation

List of Acronyms

BCG	Boston Consulting Group
CHE	chemistry
D	deliverable
ECA	European Court of Auditors
ECO	economic sciences
ENG	information science and engineering
ENV	environment and geosciences
EU	European Union
FM	final meeting
FSTP	financial support to third parties
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IBAN	international bank account number
ID	identification
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations
KO	kick-off meeting
LIF	life sciences
MAT	mathematics
MS	milestone meeting
NACE	Nomenclature of Economic Activities
OLAF	European Anti-Fraud Office
PHY	physics
PSS	product service system
SME	small to medium enterprise
SOC	social sciences and humanities
SWIFT	Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunications
SWOT	strengths weaknesses opportunities threats
T	task
UK	United Kingdom
VAT	value added tax

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I. Overview

Deliverable D3.1 – Documentation for Application Process represents a culmination of activities under task T3.1 involving the preparation of documents and form templates included in the process of collecting Challenges and Motivation Letters. These documents have been prepared during development process of INDUSAC Methodology beta version (D1.4; Odic et al., 2023a), INDUSAC User Journeys (D1.3; Rudolph et al., 2023) and INDUSAC Methodology (D1.6; Odic et al., 2023b). The documents included in this deliverable will either be part of, or uploaded to, the INDUSAC platform. Selected supporting documents may be listed in both the Call for Companies and the Call for Students/Researchers, as they are relevant for both. Templates are subject to upgrades based on feedback from end users, i.e. companies and co-creation teams, and will take place in parallel to the iterative improvement of the methodology. The documentation included in this version of the deliverable corresponds to the version 1 of the D1.6 INDUSAC Methodology (Odic et al., 2023b) originally submitted in October 2023; any changes brought about by updating the methodology will be included in the final version of D1.6 to be submitted in July 2025.

II. APPLICATION PROCESS DOCUMENTS

1. Invitation to Universities: Invitation Letter

Subject: Your support to INDUSAC Industry-Academia Collaborations

April 2023

Dear Sir or Madam,

On behalf of [organisation] and the INDUSAC project, we would like to formally invite your university/research organisation to participate in an exciting new project aimed at strengthening the collaboration between industry and academia.

INDUSAC is a HORIZON EUROPE project that aims to develop and validate an Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism. Within the project, we will facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows the development of solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries¹.

Students and researchers will create international teams of at least 3 members that will solve companies' challenges within 4-8 weeks. INDUSAC has a budget of 900,000 EUR intended for student members of co-creation teams, where mini-grants of 3,000 EUR will be distributed among student members of each team. By solving companies' challenges, students will get international working experiences, collaborative experiences by working with students and researchers from different countries, transversal and entrepreneurial skills (communication, negotiation, results orientation, responsibility, creativity, planning skills, analytical thinking, among others) access to companies across the EU, references, and a certificate of participation from INDUSAC. By participating in co-creation teams, researchers will gain companies' and students' contacts, letters of recommendation from industry partners, and a certificate of participation from INDUSAC.

In support of this project, we would kindly ask your organisation to sign the attached Letter of support. This letter will show your willingness to promote the INDUSAC opportunities

¹ Widening and associated countries: Widening countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia; [source](#)) and Associated Countries (1. Albania, 2. Armenia, 3. Bosnia and Herzegovina, 4. Faroe Islands, 5. Georgia, 6. Iceland, 7. Israel, 8. Kosovo, 9. Moldova, 10. Montenegro, 11. North Macedonia, 12. Norway, 13. Serbia, 14. Tunisia, 15. Turkey, 16. Ukraine, 17. UK).

among your students and researchers, and will serve as a foundation for future collaboration.

If you agree to sign the attached Letter of Support, please add your official letterhead/logo of your organisation and send it back to us, together with the logo of your organisation. Your logo will be displayed on the project's website (www.indusac.eu) among the logos of the other supporting organisations.

INDUSAC partners will provide you with all the necessary promo materials (mostly e-format) about INDUSAC opportunities that you can distribute among your students and researchers. No financial obligations shall take place.

We would be honoured to gain your organisation's support for this project, and we would be happy to provide you with more information about the project and its goals. If you are interested in learning more, please do not hesitate to contact us at indusac@ijs.si.

Yours sincerely,

Partners of the INDUSAC consortium

2. Invitation to Universities: Letter of Support Template

<Insert the logo of your University>

LETTER OF SUPPORT

Place, date: _____

To: Partners of the INDUSAC consortium

With this letter, we would like to express the support of our organization,
_____ (insert the organisation name), for the
HORIZON EUROPE project "INDUSAC" (INDUSAC has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon Europe Programme under the Grant Agreement No. 101070297).

We confirm our willingness to promote the INDUSAC opportunities among our students
and researchers.

We are looking forward to future collaboration.

Name of Legal Representative (eg. Rector/Director)

Signature and stamp

INDUSAC project

Partners of the INDUSAC consortium

3. Call for Companies

Call for Companies

INDUSAC OPEN CALL FOR COMPANIES

Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Call: A HUMAN-CENTRED AND ETHICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL AND INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES 2021 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01)

The call is managed by EU project INDUSAC under Horizon Europe programme. The Horizon Europe project INDUSAC, aims to financially support short-term (four to eight weeks) research collaborations between academia (students and researchers) and industry (companies), in solving company Challenges. Financial support in the form of financial support to third parties (FSTP) is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams.

Expected outcome: 300 successful collaborations between industry and academia.

Companies are invited to provide Challenges to receive Solutions from the co-creation teams (students and researchers) within four to eight weeks after the selection process of teams is finished.

Opening date: October 2023

Deadline model: single-stage, three cut-off dates

Deadline for submitting a Challenge: Companies issue Challenges continuously from the call opening date up to one of the cut-off dates:

- 15.12.2023,
- 15.04.2024,
- 15.09.2024.

Eligibility

Companies established in the EU as well as companies established in associated countries will be eligible to issue Challenges: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, Morocco, UK.

There are no restrictions on the sector, type, or size of a company to issue a Challenge (startups and large enterprises may apply as well as SMEs).

English is the official language of all INDUSAC documents using the Latin alphabet.

Application and implementation process

Step 1 - Registration on the INDUSAC Platform

The registration process (please refer to Annex 4 in this document) allows a company to create a profile and publish a Challenge on the INDUSAC platform. During the registration, the company is invited to provide certain information about the company, and verify that a company accepts the terms and conditions of this Call.

Step 2 - Issuing a Challenge on the INDUSAC Platform

On the INDUSAC platform, the company selects from nine different Challenge templates (please refer to Annex 5 in this document): (1) Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow, (2) Finding white spots in the product portfolio, (3) Marketing campaign of the future, (4) Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis, (5) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona), (6) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios), (7) Business plan - reduce your risk and optimise your planning, (8) Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain, and (9) Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS (product service system). The Challenge templates - among other information - ask for the following:

- title of the Challenge,
- description of the problem with additional explanations of key terms,
- expectations - what does the company expect in terms of solution, impact and type of collaboration with the co-creation team,
- desired co-creation team profile - which skills are desired in solving the Challenge,
- the maximum number of co-creation teams that the company can work with.

Challenges, together with the company's name, country and website will be publicly available and have to include only non-confidential information.

The Challenges issued before 15.12.2023 will be eligible for receiving possible solutions by the co-creation teams by May 2024. The Challenges issued before 15.04.2024 will be eligible for receiving possible solutions by the co-creation teams by September 2024. The Challenges issued after 15.09.2024 will be eligible for receiving possible solutions by the co-creation teams by February 2025.

Step 3 - Selection of co-creation teams

Within this step, the company selects the most suitable co-creation teams through selection of their Motivation Letter (please refer to Annex 6 in this document). Motivation Letters will be evaluated based on Team's motivation, Excellence score, Impact score, Team and resources, and Transversal criteria (Table 1).

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams; see also Annex 7 of this document):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the four to eight weeks time frame?

(5) TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

Table 1 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Motivation Letters

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring in points	Max scoring with weighting
Motivation	5%	5	0,25
Excellence	30%	5	1,5
Impact	30%	5	1,5
Team and resources	30%	5	1,5
Transversal criteria	5%	5	0,25

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Excellence, 2 Impact, 3 Team and Resources, 4 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores. A ranking list will be prepared. INDUSAC will provide companies with pre-defined justifications for rejecting Motivation Letters.

Step 4 - Implementation of co-creation projects

INDUSAC will provide the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams will be provided with a planned timeline / mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge. These instructions will be customised for each Challenge type.

Throughout the process, the company should have a kick-off meeting, at least one (highly recommended between one and three) milestone meeting and a final meeting with each co-creation team. In addition to the meetings, the company will be available, within reasonable limits, to answer students / researchers' questions (through agreed-upon channels, eg. phone, email, Zoom, the INDUSAC platform chat, etc.) regarding their tasks, and to supply further information needed to solve the task. If the students have multiple ideas, the company will assist in steering the co-creation team in the most promising direction; the company will also give insight into ideas that have already been tried in the past and failed. The company's availability for additional assistance (beyond the milestone meetings) is not mandatory but it is recommended as it is in the interest of obtaining an optimal solution.

Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects by INDUSAC

Throughout the process, the company and the co-creation teams may be approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance.

On a more general level, a Monitoring Committee will be monitoring the performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and bring to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Step 5 - Reporting

Once the co-creation project implementation is completed, the co-creation team submits an implementation report (please refer to Annex 8 in this document). The company provides feedback on the INDUSAC process through the INDUSAC platform (please refer to Annex 9 in this document) that will include:

- Deliverable quality assessment of the Solution submitted by the co-creation team
The company evaluates the deliverable quality of the submitted Solution (30% of the overall score), Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.
- Questionnaire “after” (please refer to Annex 10 in this document)
 - Questionnaire
 - Testimonial

Timeline

For receiving Motivation Letters in February 2024 and Solutions in May 2024, companies need to submit Challenges by 15.12.2023 (first cut-off date) so as to have them published by 31.12.2023.

For receiving Motivation Letters in June 2024 and Solutions in September 2024, companies need to submit Challenges by 14.04.2024 (second cut-off date) so as to have them published by 30.04.2024.

For receiving Motivation Letters in November 2024 and Solutions in February 2025, companies need to submit Challenges after 15.12.2023 and up to 15.09.2024 (third cut-off date) so as to have them published by 30.09.2024.

Terms and Conditions for companies

Number of Challenges issued

A company may issue more than one Challenge.

Compliance with European Council Implementing Decision (on Hungarian entities)

The company confirms that it is not in conflict with the European Council Implementing Decision 2022/2506 in regards to funding Hungarian entities, which stipulates that legal commitments must not be entered into with any public interest trusts established on the basis of the Hungarian Act IX of 2021 or any entity maintained by such a public interest trust. This applies as of 16.12.2022 for as long as the measures are in place. The company confirms that it is not associated with any of the affected entities listed on the Hungarian national legislation website (<https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2021-9-00-00>).

Confidentiality

The company confirms that the text, data and other content of the Challenges is non-confidential.

For cases where companies wish to share with the selected co-creation teams its confidential information, they are advised to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with the co-creation team before the start of the co-creation project.

INDUSAC partners who have access to the co-creation projects and co-creation results, have signed the Statement on Non-Disclosure of Information and Impartiality (please refer to Annex 20 in this document) and all non-public and personal data will be treated in confidence.

Intellectual Property

The company confirms that the material shared by the company representatives is owned by the company they represent and / or they have acquired the rights for their usage.

Should the cooperation between students/researchers and the company give rise to any form of intellectual property (for example, a patent application), division of ownership of intellectual property rights (based on individual parties' contributions), the type of intellectual property, and management of said intellectual property, shall be defined in a separate agreement on joint inventions. The parties (company, co-creation team) agree to the following provisions:

- On the basis of the undisputed fact that an invention presents a result of joint collaboration of student/researcher and the company and that student/researcher and the company were involved in the process of creation and development of the invention, the invention shall be considered as a joint invention of student/researcher and the company.
- Any intellectual property developed prior to the solving of a Challenge belongs to the party that developed it.
- Procedures such as registration and maintenance of the intellectual property shall be coordinated by the company.
- Students must follow the guidelines set by the company in regards to intellectual property disclosure and ownership; they may sign a statement waiving their economic intellectual property rights, by which they are exempt from any financial obligations towards protection of said intellectual property rights (such as, for example, preparation, registration / filing, processing, expansion, and maintenance fees); they may opt to retain authorship rights only, in which case they remain co-authors on the invention but receive no material benefits.
- Researchers must follow appropriate invention disclosure legislation, which may include disclosing the invention to their employer and subsequently transferring intellectual property rights to the employer.
- Regardless of status and intellectual property rights transfers, student/researcher retains the right to be listed as co-author on the invention.

The parties (company, student, researcher) agree that each party, individually or together with the remaining party, may use the invention for the purpose of its own research, without restrictions and without any obligation to remunerate the other party in any form or manner. The parties agree that the results of the co-creation project, except the INDUSAC requirements, will not be published, commercialised or otherwise allowed to be used by third parties without written agreement by all parties.

Long-term relevance of Challenges

For all issued Challenges, the companies acknowledge that Motivation Letters will be evaluated at three cut-off dates and that their Challenge, regardless of how soon it was issued, must still be relevant for the first upcoming cut-off date.

Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with:

- the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity).
- applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Based on the Horizon Europe Ethic Self-Assessment guidance (European Commission, 2021) the company must ensure that the activities under the action do not include the following:

- human embryonic stem cells
- human embryos
- human fetal tissues/cells
- cause harm to the environment, animals, or plants
- military applications
- malevolent / criminal / terrorist abuse

The company may decide to reject a proposed Motivation Letter. The company assures that any rejections of Motivation Letters will be based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters (following the INDUSAC evaluation criteria) and not be affected by the co-creation teams' gender or citizenship/residency.

If a co-creation team has provided draft Solutions or Solution proposals in applying to a Challenge, but ends up rejected, the company commits to discarding the rejected proposal without any further use of the solutions proposed therein.

Values

All parties must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Conflict of interests

The company must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the co-creation project could be compromised for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').

The company confirms that it is not giving preferential treatment in regards to Motivation Letters / Solutions based on the applicant's professional or personal connections with the company and that approval is based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters / Solutions.

Disputes and exits

The parties (companies, students and researchers) agree that they will conclude in writing any amendments to any existing arrangements, and will endeavour to resolve any disputes regarding this arrangement in a peaceful manner. In the event that the parties cannot resolve the dispute individually, the INDUSAC coordinator shall mediate over the dispute.

In the co-creation process exit points of companies, students and researchers are foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

Keeping records and supporting documents

The company acknowledges that it can substantiate the proper implementation of the action by records and other supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations.

The company can provide written proof, if required from INDUSAC partners, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Communication, Dissemination And Visibility

Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the INDUSAC, communication activities of the parties (company, students, researcher) related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities or major results implemented under the INDUSAC must acknowledge INDUSAC and EU support and display the INDUSAC logo, European flag (emblem) and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Graphic guide to use EU logo is available here:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains:

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] represents the author’s view only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”.

Supporting documentation:

- Registration Form for Companies (please refer to Annex 4 in this document)
- Challenge Types (please refer to Annex 5 in this document)
- Motivation Letter Template (please refer to Annex 6 in this document)
- Template for Evaluation of Motivation Letters (please refer to Annex 7 in this document)
- Template for Co-Creation Implementation Report (please refer to Annex 8 in this document)
- Template for Evaluation of Solutions (please refer to Annex 9 in this document)
- Questionnaire for Companies after completion of the Co-creation Project (please refer to Annex 10 in this document)
- Statement on Non-disclosure of Information and Impartiality for INDUSAC Partners (please refer to Annex 20 in this document)

4. Registration Form for Companies

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for companies

Marked with ** for data that will be visible on the public part of the platform without the login

- ****Name of the company**
- Address of the company
- ****Country** (drop down menu of eligible countries: all EU countries and all Associated countries)
- VAT number
- ID number
- Name of legal representative
- E-mail of legal representative (must be an official organisation email rather than general or personal address, such as Gmail or similar)
- ****Website**
- Name of contact person
- E-mail of contact person
- Nr. of employees (tick suitable box: 0-10, 11-50, 50-250, 250-1,000, more than 1,000) also for statistical purposes
- NACE code (for statistical purposes): A - Agriculture, forestry and fishing, B - Mining and quarrying, C - Manufacturing, D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, E - Water supply; sewerage; waste management and remediation activities, F - Construction, G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, H - Transporting and storage, I - Accommodation and food service activities, J - Information and communication, K - Financial and insurance activities, L - Real estate activities, M - Professional, scientific and technical activities, N - Administrative and support service activities, O - Public administration and defence; compulsory social security, P - Education, Q - Human health and social work activities, R - Arts, entertainment and recreation, S - Other services activities, T - Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods - and services - producing activities of households for own use, U - Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies
- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Companies
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (company data, such as specific contacts, to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published)

5. Challenge Types (1-9)

Challenge type 1: Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust² product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis³.

Long description:

In this challenge, the teams will derive future-robust product properties based on scenarios or a trend analysis. If you have already identified scenarios, you can provide them to the teams. If that is not the case their challenge will be based on a trend analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). At the KO, you will get to know each other and have the chance to set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. In the next phase, the team will analyse the current product features in the product portfolio and present them in a first milestone meeting (MS1). The team then will focus on analysing the future. If scenarios are given to the team, they will base their research on these. Otherwise, their analysis will be based on trends that the teams will identify through their research. This is followed by a second milestone meeting (MS2), where you give feedback to the team on their findings. In the final phase, the teams derive future-robust product properties and prioritise them based on a cost-benefit analysis. A product property is considered future-robust if it appears in multiple scenarios or trends. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before the final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They will be able to choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed, to ensure the solution is developed in the desired direction. If you would like to know more

² The future robustness results from the combined consideration of the weighted relevance of a product characteristic and its standard deviation. A high degree of future robustness indicates that the technical realisation of a product feature will make a major contribution to customer satisfaction even if various developments occur in the environment.

³ A trend analysis makes it possible to analyse and depict social developments and their possible effects on companies. A trend as a (probable) future development first creates a feeling of being at the mercy of our environment and shows us that we cannot act independently of our environment. This unpleasant feeling is mitigated by counteracting the uncertainty about the future. The presentation of observable trends and their evaluation in terms of probability of occurrence and impact on an element under consideration help in this.

about the information provided, please click [here](#) (Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students (specific for each Challenge type)).

Figure 1 : Process timeline Challenge type 1

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Scenario/trend analysis and references (e.g. Word)
- Catalogue of future robust product properties (e.g. Excel)

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

Title

Picture

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

***Context: 50 - 200 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear?

What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem context.

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Aerospace +

Agriculture and Marine Resources +

Agrofood Industry +

Biological Sciences +

Communications +

Computer related +

Consumer related +

Digitalization +

Electronics Related Market +

Electronics, IT and Telecomms +

Energy Market +

Energy Technology +

Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology +

Industrial Products +

Industrial Technologies +

Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies +

Lightweight +

Measurements and Standards +

Medical Health related +

Ophthalmology +

Other +

Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences +

Protecting Man and Environment +

Social and Economics concerns +

Sustainability +

Figure 2 : Categorization of Challenge type 1

Do you have scenarios/already known trends available to give to the teams to further develop them?

*Input: 5 - 50 words

*Expectations⁴: 10 - 100 words

Desired team profile⁵: 10 - 20 words

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions)?

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

⁴ Do you expect that the solution will target a specific market?

Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient?

⁵ computer scientist, students who speak Romanian (if the target is the Romanian market), CAD skills... etc.

Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Would you like the teams to explore a specific direction or market?

Do you have any discarded solutions already?

What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

- 👤 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*). Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers (*linked to the call for companies and linked to the call for students and researchers*), and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any additional agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers prevail.

- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
- Create an additional submission agreement

*🔒 Privacy settings for this Challenge

- Post as [Name sub-user] from Company
- Post as Company

Challenge type 2: Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Finding white spots⁶ in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's⁷ elements based on a strategic analysis⁸ of the product portfolio.

Long description:

In this challenge, the teams will develop an action plan on how to close white spots in your product portfolio based on a strategic analysis of your product portfolio. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, the team will analyse your product portfolio in terms of product families or business units. Having positioned the products in terms of their importance in the market, they will target the clusters that need improvement. They will present the identified product clusters in a first milestone meeting (MS1). The teams will then focus on the white spots and refine them to derive an action plan. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each Challenge type\)](#)).

⁶ White spots are for example gaps or opportunities in a market that are currently underserved or not addressed by existing products or services in a company's product portfolio.

⁷ A product portfolio describes the complete product range that a company provides on the market. The product portfolio can consist of a single product or multiple products, which can either be defined by a product diversification of a certain product or by completely different products. A combination of the mentioned diversifications is possible.

⁸ A portfolio analysis can be conducted based on existing or potential products, projects, resources, and knowledge within a company's portfolio. They are evaluated regarding the market attractiveness and competitive position of the company. From this, statements are derived on how intensively a company should invest in the marketing of individual products or product groups. The result of a portfolio analysis is a simple graphic representation (portfolio display) of complex relationships.

The best-known portfolio representations are:

Boston Consulting Group Portfolio (BSG-Portfolio, Four-field matrix)

McKinsey Portfolio (Nine-field-Matrix)

Figure 3 : Process timeline of Challenge type 2

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Strategic analysis of product portfolio (e.g. BCG-matrix)
- Clustering of product portfolio (e.g. PowerPoint)
- Action-plan⁹/white spot analysis¹⁰ for relevant clusters

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

⁹ An action plan lists specific action steps to achieve the goal of filling the white spots in the product portfolio.

¹⁰ A white spot analysis identifies gaps or opportunities in a market that are currently underserved or not addressed by existing products or services in a company's product portfolio. This can be done by analysing demographic data, consumer surveys, sales data, and conducting other market research.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

Title

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Picture

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Do not disclose any classified technical or business information since challenges will be visible on a public website.

*Context: 50 - 200 words

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

*Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear?
What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem context.*

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Type in a search term

Aerospace +

Agriculture and Marine Resources +

Agrofood Industry +

Biological Sciences +

Communications +

Computer related +

Consumer related +

Digitalization +

Electronics Related Market +

Electronics, IT and Telecomms +

Energy Market +

Energy Technology +

Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology +

Industrial Products +

Industrial Technologies +

Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies +

Lightweight +

Measurements and Standards +

Medical Health related +

Ophthalmology +

Other +

Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences +

Protecting Man and Environment +

Social and Economics concerns +

Sustainability +

Figure 4 : Categorization of Challenge type 2

Do you have a presentation of your product portfolio which you can share with the team? Do you have future product ideas which the team should consider?

*Input: 5 - 50 words

*Expectations¹¹: 10 - 100 words

Desired team profile¹²: 10 - 20 words

*In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve?
Would you like the teams to explore a specific direction or market?*

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

¹¹ Do you expect that the solution will target a specific market?

Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient?

¹² Marketing specialists, students who speak Romanian (if the target is the Romanian market), analytical skills... etc.

Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/ researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions)?

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

- Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*). Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

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- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
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- Post as Company

Challenge type 3: Marketing campaign of the future

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis¹³ with a focus on customers and trend analysis¹⁴.^①

Long description:

In this challenge, the teams will create a marketing campaign that targets your future customers. They will base their assumptions on market, customer, and trend analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will analyse and understand today's customers and then look at future customers. They will also analyse your current marketing strategy to get a deeper understanding of it as a basis for future campaigns. They will present their findings up to this point in the first milestone (MS1). Based on their findings and your feedback, they will focus on future trends and start creating the marketing campaign. This will be based on future customers and trends and will be in line with your corporate marketing strategy. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The suggested methods and templates will also be provided to the teams. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution is developed in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each Challenge type\)](#)).

¹³ A market analysis studies the attractiveness and dynamics of a market within an industry. It focuses on changes in customer needs and customer behaviour. It also considers competitors, their goals and their strategies which play a central role. A market analysis can be conducted through a SWOT analysis.

¹⁴ With a trend analysis, changes in social values and currents of different social classes can be determined and their effect on companies.

On this basis, statements about future developments can be made and suitable proposals for product policy and marketing strategies can be developed.

Figure 5 : Process timeline Challenge type 3

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Market analysis with a focus on customers
- Trend analysis combining future customers and marketing trends
- Design of a marketing campaign

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

Title

*Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words

Picture

*Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:

*Short description: 50 - 100 words

Describe your challenge briefly.

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Do not disclose any classified technical or business information since challenges will be visible on a public website.

*Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words

*Context: 50 - 200 words

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Type in a search term

Aerospace + Agriculture and Marine Resources + Agrofood Industry + Biological Sciences + Communications + Computer related + Consumer related + Digitalization + Electronics Related Market + Electronics, IT and Telecomms + Energy Market + Energy Technology + Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology + Industrial Products + Industrial Technologies + Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies + Lightweight + Measurements and Standards + Medical Health related + Ophthalmology + Other + Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences + Protecting Man and Environment + Social and Economics concerns + Sustainability +

Figure 6 : Categorization of Challenge type 3

*Input: 5 - 50 words

*Do you have already known trends available to give to the teams for further development?
Do you have an existing marketing campaign which was a success, or which clearly did not deliver the results you expected?*

*In which direction do you expect the marketing campaign to evolve?
Would you like the team to explore a specific direction or market?
Do you have any discarded solutions already?
What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?*

*Expectations¹⁵: 10 - 100 words

Desired team profile¹⁶: 10 - 20 words

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

*Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.:
Competitive situation in the sector specific to this challenge/ Marketing Campaigns you consider to
be best practice examples/ Trends you may have already identified/ Details about your customer
groups)?*

*To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to
provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.*

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*).

¹⁵ Do you expect that the solution will target a specific market?
Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient?
Do you expect a digital, offline, or mixed marketing campaign? Do you expect the team to include social media in the campaign?

¹⁶ Marketing specialist, students who speak Italian (if the target is the Italian market), creative minds, experience with working with different cultures... etc.

Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers (*linked to the call for companies and linked to the call for students and researchers*), and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any additional agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers prevail.

- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
- Create an additional submission agreement

* **Privacy settings for this Challenge**

- Post as [Name sub-user] from Company
- Post as Company

Challenge type 4: Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype¹⁷ based on a market analysis¹⁸.

Long description:

In this challenge, the team will build a prototype of a new platform for your company based on a market analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). At the KO, you will get to know each other and have the chance to set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, the teams will identify the products or services for which your company needs the platform and determine your requirements. In the first milestone meeting (MS1), the team will present their current findings and align with your company representative on the goal of the platform. The next step is to analyse the market in terms of competitors and your company's marketing and sales strategy. The team presents their findings in a second milestone meeting (MS2). In the final phase, they conceptualise the platform and build a virtual prototype. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They will be able to choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed, to ensure the solution is developed in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each Challenge type\)](#)).

¹⁷ A prototype visualizes mental ideas and supports the understanding of complexity. It is built to validate potential solutions. Furthermore, prototypes enable communication and thus help overcome for example cultural and language barriers. Prototypes are built to answer a specific question and are restricted to given boundary conditions. They also test functionalities and requirements.

In this case, the goal is the development of a click dummy or mock-up of a digital platform.

¹⁸ A market analysis studies the attractiveness and the dynamics of a market within an industry. It focuses on changes in customer needs and customer behaviour. It also considers competitors, their goals and their strategies which play a central role. It is part of the industry analysis and thus in turn of the global environmental analysis but can also be conducted individually. A market analysis can be conducted through a SWOT analysis.

Figure 7 : Process timeline Challenge type 4

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Market analysis to define the platform
- Digital Platform prototype (click dummy) (based on existing product profiles)

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

Title

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Picture

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

Do not disclose any classified technical or business information since challenges will be visible on a public website.

*Context: 50 - 200 words

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Aerospace +

Agriculture and Marine Resources +

Agrofood Industry +

Biological Sciences +

Communications +

Computer related +

Consumer related +

Digitalization +

Electronics Related Market +

Electronics, IT and Telecomms +

Energy Market +

Energy Technology +

Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology +

Industrial Products +

Industrial Technologies +

Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies +

Lightweight +

Measurements and Standards +

Medical Health related +

Ophthalmology +

Other +

Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences +

Protecting Man and Environment +

Social and Economics concerns +

Sustainability +

Figure 8 : Categorization of Challenge type 4

*Input: 5 - 50 words

Which digital platforms are relevant as references? Do you have a website/ another type of online sales channel that should be used as a reference? Do you have prior market research results you want to make available to the student teams?

*Expectations¹⁹: 10 - 100 words

*In which direction do you expect the digital platform to evolve?
 Would you like the students to use a specific platform tool?
 Do you have any discarded solutions already?
 What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?*

¹⁹ Do you expect that the solution will have any specific features?
 Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient?

Desired team profile²⁰: 10 - 20 words

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

reference/ Tools you can supply the students with)?

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*). Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers (*linked to the call for companies and linked to the call for students and researchers*), and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any additional agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers prevail.

- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
- Create an additional submission agreement

* Privacy settings for this Challenge

- Post as [Name sub-user] from Company
- Post as Company

²⁰ Marketing specialists, students who speak Romanian (if the target is the Romanian market), CAD/programming skills... etc. Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Challenge type 5: Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea²¹ based on one or multiple personas²², and appropriate product properties.

Long description:

In this challenge, the students will derive new service or product ideas for your company based on an analysis of your relevant target group. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will analyse your target group and create Personas to better understand your customers. In a first milestone meeting (MS1), they will present the Personas to your company representative to ensure that they have correctly understood the company's customer profiles. Based on the Personas, they will derive several product ideas. The team will work out a maximum of three detailed service or product ideas. In the second milestone meeting (MS2), they will present these services or ideas and you will decide together which of these ideas they should analyse further with a value proposition analysis. The value proposition will be the core of the next and last phase. In the final meeting (FM) the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before the final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each Challenge type\)](#)).

²¹ A product idea is a possibility of how to realize the characteristics of the product defined in a product profile. Part of a product idea is the product claim, product description, picture, functional structure, system structure, validation, and satisfaction of customer and user, as well as strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the idea. The students solving this challenge will get templates to specify product ideas and product profiles.

²² Personas are fictive persons who are typical representatives of a target group. The students solving this challenge will get templates to create personas.

Figure 9 : Process timeline Challenge type 5

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Persona
- Product Profile²³
- Service/ Product idea

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

²³ A product profile is a model of a bundle of benefits, which makes the desired supplier, customer, and user benefits accessible for validation and explicitly specifies the solution space for the design of a product generation.

A bundle of benefits is understood as a set of products and services that is created with the purpose of being created to be sold to a customer and to directly or indirectly create benefits for him - e.g., for users considered by him or for his customers.

The students solving this challenge will get templates to create product profiles.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

Title

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Picture

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

***Context: 50 - 200 words**

*Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear
What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem context.*

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

***Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words**

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Type in a search term

Figure 10 : Categorization of Challenge type 5

***Input: 5 - 50 words**

Are there existing target groups which you have already identified and want the personas to focus on? Do you have additional information you want to supply the teams with?

***Expectations²⁴: 10 - 100 words**

*In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve?
 Would you like the students to target a specific customer group?
 Do you have any discarded product or service ideas already?
 What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?*

Desired team profile²⁵: 10 - 20 words

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

²⁴ For example: Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient?

²⁵ Marketing specialists, students who speak Romanian (if the target is the Romanian market), analytical thinking... etc. Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions).

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

Select challenge manager

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

- 👤 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*). Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers (*linked to the call for companies and linked to the call for students and researchers*), and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any additional agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers prevail.

- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
- Create an additional submission agreement

*🔒 Privacy settings for this Challenge

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- Post as Company

Challenge type 6: Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea²⁶ based on one or multiple trends/scenarios²⁷, and appropriate future-robust product properties²⁸.

Long description:

In this challenge, the students will derive new service or product ideas for your company based on scenarios or a trend analysis. If you have already identified scenarios, you can provide them to the student teams. If that is not the case their challenge will be based on a trend analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. The teams then focus on analysing the future. If the students are given scenarios, they will base their research on these. Otherwise, their analysis will be based on trends that the teams have identified through their research. This is followed by a first milestone meeting (MS1) where you give feedback to the team on their findings. Based on the trends or scenarios, they will derive several product ideas and work out the best ones. In the second milestone meeting (MS2), they will present these services or ideas to you, and you will decide together which of these ideas they should analyse further with a value proposition analysis. The value proposition will be the next and last phase. In the final meeting (FM) the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the

²⁶ A product idea is a possibility of how to realize the characteristics of the product defined in a product profile. Part of a product idea is the product claim, product description, picture, functional structure, system structure, validation, and satisfaction of customer and user, as well as strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the idea. The students solving this challenge will get templates to specify product ideas and product profiles.

²⁷ Scenarios describe possible manifestations of the future based on various development possibilities of several networked key factors.

²⁸ The future robustness results from the combined consideration of the weighted relevance of a product characteristic and its standard deviation. A high degree of future robustness indicates that the technical realisation of a product feature will make a major contribution to customer satisfaction even if various developments occur in the environment.

information provided, please click [here](#) (Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students (specific for each Challenge type)).

Figure 11 : Process timeline Challenge type 6

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Persona
- Product Profile²⁹ ⓘ
- Service/ Product idea

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

²⁹ A product profile is a model of a bundle of benefits, which makes the desired supplier, customer, and user benefits accessible for validation and explicitly specifies the solution space for the design of a product generation.

A bundle of benefits is understood as a set of products and services that is created with the purpose of being created to be sold to a customer and to directly or indirectly create benefits for him - e.g., for users considered by him or for his customers.

The students solving this challenge will get templates to create product profiles.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

Title

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Picture

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

***Context: 50 - 200 words**

*Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear
What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem context.*

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Type in a search term

Aerospace +

Agriculture and Marine Resources +

Agrofood Industry +

Biological Sciences +

Communications +

Computer related +

Consumer related +

Digitalization +

Electronics Related Market +

Electronics, IT and Telecomms +

Energy Market +

Energy Technology +

Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology +

Industrial Products +

Industrial Technologies +

Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies +

Lightweight +

Measurements and Standards +

Medical Health related +

Ophthalmology +

Other +

Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences +

Protecting Man and Environment +

Social and Economics concerns +

Sustainability +

Figure 12 : Categorization of Challenge type 6

*Input: 5 - 50 words

If you have identified scenarios already, please provide them to the teams. The challenge can be solved based on scenarios you give as input or on trends the teams identify and analyse. Please clarify which option you want the teams to use.

*Expectations³⁰: 10 - 100 words

In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve?
Do you have any discarded solutions already?

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Desired team profile³¹: 10 - 20 words

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Trends or Megatrends relevant for your sector)?

³⁰ For example: Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient?

³¹ Diverse team regarding academic background, students who speak Romanian (if the target is the Romanian market), analytical thinking... etc. Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

- 👤 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*). Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers (*linked to the call for companies and linked to the call for students and researchers*), and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any additional agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers prevail.

- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
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Challenge type 7: Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan³² after a SWOT analysis³³ and an estimation of profitability.

Long description:

In this challenge, the students will develop a business plan after a SWOT analysis and will then estimate the profitability of the business plan they've developed. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will conduct a SWOT analysis of your business in total and determine how each finding impacts the business and its goals. They determine if a finding is positive or negative and identify any areas of concern that may need to be addressed in the business plan. In a first milestone meeting (MS1), the team presents the findings to your company representative to make sure early in the process, that they understood the goals of the company. Within this milestone, you can see how the analysis develops and guide the team in the right direction. Based on their results, they will prepare a business model canvas and write a business plan that fixes the weaknesses and threats identified in the SWOT analysis and pushes the opportunities and strengths to the next level. They will present the business plan in the second milestone meeting (MS2) and discuss it with your company representative. Based on the feedback from the milestone meeting and their findings, they will evaluate the business plan with an estimation of the profitability of the business. This is followed by a final milestone meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do

³² A business plan focuses on major areas of concern and their contribution to the success of a new business. The finished plan communicates the product or service to others and provides the basis for the financial proposal. The plan identifies customers, target markets, pricing strategy, and competitive conditions. It aids in decision-making and is an essential guide for operating a business successfully and measuring progress. The business plan not only serves as a mechanism for obtaining any needed financial resources but also indicates the future direction of the company.

³³ SWOT analysis (or SWOT matrix) is a strategic planning and strategic management technique used to help a person or organization identify Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats related to business competition or project planning.

so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here (Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students (specific for each Challenge type)).

Figure 13 : Process timeline Challenge type 7

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- SWOT-Analysis
- Business plan
- Estimation of profitability

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and Product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and Product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

Title

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Picture

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear

What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem context.

***Context: 50 - 200 words**

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Type in a search term

Aerospace + Agriculture and Marine Resources + Agrofood Industry + Biological Sciences + Communications + Computer related +
 Consumer related + Digitalization + Electronics Related Market + Electronics, IT and Telecomms + Energy Market +
 Energy Technology + Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology + Industrial Products + Industrial Technologies +
 Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies + Lightweight + Measurements and Standards + Medical Health related +
 Ophthalmology + Other + Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences + Protecting Man and Environment + Social and Economics concerns +
 Sustainability +

Figure 14 : Categorization of Challenge type 7

*Input: 5 - 50 words

Do you have former business plans that you want the teams to use as input? Do you prefer specific tools you can supply the teams with for the estimation of profitability?

*In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve?
 Do you want the teams to focus on a specific business unit?
 Do you have any discarded solutions already?
 What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?*

*Expectations³⁴: 10 - 100 words

Desired team profile³⁵: 10 - 20 words

³⁴ Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient? Do you expect them to use specific methods of calculation?

³⁵ Experience with financial analysis, analytical thinking, diverse academic background... etc. Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

Which details/info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this Challenge/ Current Mergers/ Acquisitions)?

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

- 👤 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

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- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
- Create an additional submission agreement

*🔒 Privacy settings for this Challenge

- Post as [Name sub-user] from Company
- Post as Company

Challenge type 8: Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas³⁶ should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype³⁷.

Long description:

In this challenge, the students will develop alternative product ideas based on specific customer needs that you provide the teams with. After a detailed analysis, they will build a prototype based on a product idea. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. In the next phase, they derive product ideas based on the given customer pain points and existing product profiles (your description and details on the customer needs that you identified before the challenge). To evaluate their ideas, they will perform a utility analysis. In the first milestone meeting (MS1), they will present their current findings. Your company representative and the team will assess which product idea should be built as a virtual prototype. The students will build the virtual prototype in the next phase. This is followed by a final milestone meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each Challenge type\)](#)).

³⁶ A product idea is a possibility of how to realize the characteristics of the product defined in a product profile. Part of a product idea is the product claim, product description, picture, functional structure, system structure, validation, and satisfaction of customer and user, as well as strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the idea. The students solving this challenge will get templates to specify product ideas and product profiles.

³⁷ A prototype visualizes mental ideas and supports the understanding of complexity. It is built to validate potential solutions. Furthermore, prototypes enable communication and thus help overcome for example cultural and language barriers. Prototypes are built to answer a specific question and are restricted to given boundary conditions. They also test functionalities and requirements. In this case, the prototype is built as a virtual prototype with the help of for example specific software (tools).

Figure 15 : Process timeline Challenge type 8

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Development of alternative product ideas
- Utility analysis³⁸ and evaluation of ideas
- Virtual prototype

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

³⁸ The utility analysis is a powerful planning method. It is used to systematically prepare decisions by evaluating (determining benefits) and selecting (ranking based on benefits) optimal alternatives (evaluation objects). It is particularly suitable for cases in which the total benefit is composed of a wide variety of partial benefits and the monetary profit is insufficient as the sole criterion for decision-making. The utility analysis allows for the collection of both objective and subjective information.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

Title

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Picture

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

*Context: 50 - 200 words

*Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear
What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem context.*

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Aerospace +

Agriculture and Marine Resources +

Agrofood Industry +

Biological Sciences +

Communications +

Computer related +

Consumer related +

Digitalization +

Electronics Related Market +

Electronics, IT and Telecomms +

Energy Market +

Energy Technology +

Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology +

Industrial Products +

Industrial Technologies +

Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies +

Lightweight +

Measurements and Standards +

Medical Health related +

Ophthalmology +

Other +

Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences +

Protecting Man and Environment +

Social and Economics concerns +

Sustainability +

Figure 16 : Categorization of Challenge type 8

*Input: 5 - 50 words

This challenge works based on a customer need you have already identified. Please specify the need here. You may give all additional information about the need/ your customers/ your target group here.

*Expectations³⁹: 10 - 100 words

³⁹ Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient? Do you expect the virtual prototype to be in a specific format? Do you expect the team to focus e.g. on Industry 4.0?

*In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve?
Would you like the students to target a specific customer group where you identified the need?
Do you have any discarded product ideas already?
What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver?*

Desired team profile⁴⁰: 10 - 20 words

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: virtual prototypes you have developed in the past)?

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*).

⁴⁰ Computer science students, programming skills, analytical thinking, creative minds... etc. Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers (*linked to the call for companies and linked to the call for students and researchers*), and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any additional agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers prevail.

- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
- Create an additional submission agreement

* **Privacy settings for this Challenge**

- Post as [Name sub-user] from Company
- Post as Company

Challenge type 9: Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS⁴¹

The development of new business models⁴² for a given product.

Long description:

In this challenge, students develop new business models for a given product. This is based on a target group analysis using the persona method. To make the challenge a success, we recommend the following process for your cooperation with the student team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will analyse your target group and create Personas to better understand your customers. In a first milestone meeting (MS1), they will present the Personas to your company representative to ensure that they have correctly understood the company's customer profiles. Based on the Personas, they will derive three alternative business models. Finally, they will evaluate the business models. This is followed by a final milestone meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each Challenge type\)](#)).

⁴¹ A Product Service System (PSS) is a market proposition that extends the traditional functionality of a product by incorporating additional services.

⁴² A business model describes the basic principle by which an organisation creates, communicates, and captures value. Business models are often displayed within a business model canvas, that structures the business idea on one page.

Figure 17 : Process timeline Challenge type 9

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Persona (user behaviour)
- Business model
- 3 alternatives and subsequent utility analysis⁴³

Post your challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates and choose one to guide you through writing your challenge.

What are you searching for?

⁴³ The utility analysis is a powerful planning method. It is used to systematically prepare decisions by evaluating (determining benefits) and selecting (ranking based on benefits) optimal alternatives (evaluation objects). It is particularly suitable for cases in which the total benefit is composed of a wide variety of partial benefits and the monetary profit is insufficient as the sole criterion for decision-making. The utility analysis allows for the collection of both objective and subjective information.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Finding white spots in the product portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

Marketing campaign of the future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The development of new business models for a given product.

***Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words**

Title

***Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:**

Picture

***Short description: 50 - 100 words**

Describe your challenge briefly.

***Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words**

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.

***Context: 50 - 200 words**

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear
 What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem context.

***Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words**

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams.

Type in a search term

Figure 18 : Categorization of Challenge type 9

***Input: 5 - 50 words**

Please use this field to give all the details needed about the product you want the teams to focus on. Exchange of files will be possible as soon as teams are selected to solve your challenge.

***Expectations⁴⁴: 10 - 100 words**

⁴⁴ Would you like the team to visit the company or are online meetings sufficient? Do you want the teams to use a specific way of displaying the business model?

*In which direction do you expect the solution to evolve?
Do you have any discarded business models already?
What do you expect from the team apart from the solution they deliver? Display of the business models within a business model canvas?*

Desired team profile⁴⁵: 10 - 20 words

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

Which details/ info would you like to give to all the teams before they write their information (e.g.: Competitive situation in the sector specific to this challenge/ Information about the main rival product)?

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*Agreement with Terms and References

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC Terms and conditions set out in the call for students and researchers (*linked to the call*). Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation.

⁴⁵ Finance specialists, creative minds, analytical thinking, experience with a specific market/industry... etc. Due to the international and inclusive character of the project and project teams you are encouraged to issue challenges accommodating students/researchers irrespective of gender or nationality.

Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers (*linked to the call for companies and linked to the call for students and researchers*), and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any additional agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC Terms and conditions for companies and INDUSAC Terms and conditions for students and researchers prevail.

- I agree on the Terms and Conditions set in the Call for companies*
- Create an additional submission agreement

***🔒 Privacy settings for this Challenge**

- Post as [Name sub-user] from Company
- Post as Company

6. Motivation Letter Form

Challenge title

Attachments

Drag and drop your files here –

Add pictures and other visuals to increase the description of your solution proposal

Please upload your resume and, if needed, further documents concerning your idea for a solution.

Possible formats: PDF, JPG, DOC, AVI, MPG4, XLS

Team ID

Please be aware that the motivation will only be processed after submission, if all linked team members confirm their participation. An automated e-mail will be sent to every team member after you submit the motivation.

Describe your team motivation

Describe your team motivation in your own words. You should include why you as a team are most suitable to find a great solution for this challenge in collaboration with the industry partner. You can use this field to give a quick introduction to all the team members and let everybody state their personal motivation for this challenge. The conclusion should answer why you as a team are well prepared to solve this challenge.

Example Conclusion: We as a team will find a great solution together since we not only come from different countries but we also study three very different degrees which will help us to think out of the box. Jane studies mechanical engineering and has a lot of experience with building physical prototypes. Tim is in his third year of an architecture bachelor's. He knows a lot about different materials, and has also been building prototypes since his first semester. Melanie studies corporate law and works in her free time for an NGO. We see ourselves as qualified not only to find an innovative solution but also to visualize it through a prototype. Furthermore, we will focus on finding a sustainable and durable solution that can be used in all countries. To make sure it fits with the different countries' regulations, Melanie uses her knowledge from a European corporate law class

How will you address the following aspects? (you may respond to all the criteria if possible) (up to 5000 characters):

Excellence

How will your team reach an excellent solution for this challenge? Why is your team one that can propose a solution that might become a real innovation?

Impact

Why do you believe your team will find a solution that can be successful on the market? To what level will your solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? You may also describe what you already found out about the companies' competition and how you are trying to get to a differentiated solution. Do you already have ideas about how a solution to this challenge might not only solve the challenge but tackle a respective structural problem? How important will the project in your opinion be for the company? Will the solution be implementable also in other sectors?

Team & Resources

Demonstrate your transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, your ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and your capacity to carry through your ideas and understand the dynamics of the market you are trying to tap into. Do you have specific resources that qualify you as a team specifically to find an excellent solution? Do you plan a visit to the companies' premises within the duration of the project? Do you plan any other travel (national or international; e.g., visiting a library, visiting a teammate, visiting a prototyping centre etc.)? How much time (hours/team member) do you plan to invest in this project?

Transversal criteria

Do you have ideas to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', "Inclusiveness" or 'Social Impact' within your way to a solution for the challenge? If yes you may describe here how or why you are planning to do so.

Idea for solution (optional)

Optional: If you already have an idea for a solution for this challenge, please briefly describe it here. Note: filling this field is optional (up to 5000 characters)

Describe the idea you have for solving this challenge as clearly as you can. It might include which technology you plan on using, procedures you believe solve the challenge, services or other details

you came already up with in your team. If applicable please make sure you are not disclosing any confidential information.

About you

7. Template for Evaluation: Motivation Letters

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 2 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Motivation Letters

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score
Team's Motivation	5 %	5	0,25	
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5	
Impact	30 %	5	1,5	
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5	
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25	
Total	100 %	25	5	

Scoring system with scores 0 to 5 (no decimals).

wherein:

- 0 - Motivation Letter makes no effort to fulfill any of the listed aspects
- 1 - Motivation Letter does not address all aspects or covers all aspects poorly
- 2 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects but at least half of them poorly
- 3 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved
- 4 - All aspects are clearly presented but could be improved
- 5 - All aspects are clearly and satisfactorily presented

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Motivation, 2 Excellence, 3 Impact, 4 Team and Resources, 5 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores.

Decision (accept / reject): _____

Justification in case of rejection (select one or more options)

- The teams' motivation is not convincing enough and several parts are poorly addressed.
- Excellence: The foreseen approach, the credibility of the proposed methodology, and the efficiency and quality of the proposed work are not convincing.
- Impact: The motivation letter does not provide information relevant or credible enough to consider that the team will be able to provide a differentiated or innovative solution that can be successful on the market or relevant for the company.
- Team and resources: One or several of the required aspects, within the team and resources, to develop a solution in a four to eight weeks time frame are missing.
- Transversal criteria: The ideas on how to include transversal criteria within the teams' way to a solution for the challenge are poorly considered.

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry

through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.

- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the 4-8 weeks time frame?

(5) TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

8. Template for Co-Creation Implementation Report

To be filled out by each member of the co-creation team (students and researchers).

Co-Creation Implementation Report	
Title of the Challenge	
Team Leader	
Team Member	
Team Member	
Start of project	(date)
End of project	(date)
<p>Short description of the project results. Please provide a short description of the project results and a short description of your personal contribution (five sentences total). Note that the description will be published on the INDUSAC website and on the EU platform so please don't include classified information.</p>	
<p>List of Deliverables prepared and uploaded on the platform</p>	
<p>Inclusiveness statement (explain in a few sentences how your solution is inclusive, ie. not excluding any groups of individuals in terms of gender, race, nationality, etc.)</p>	
<p> </p>	

Upskilling, clarity and satisfaction questionnaire

Testimonial: please provide a short testimonial, e.g. a letter or written statement of recommendation of something given or done as an expression of esteem, admiration, or gratitude. See two examples below:

“The company that issued the Challenge is active in the services sector. Due to a low number of employees and a busy schedule, it is a Challenge for them to find time to think out-of-the box. Within the INDUSAC co-creation project team, we not only got an opportunity to solve a real-life company problem and provide ideas for improved services but also got experience in international cooperation with fellow students and researchers. We would be happy to participate in similar initiatives in the future!”

“I learned about the INDUSAC at the university where I study. Then I checked the INDUSAC website and there were several Challenges from companies. Three Challenges were really interesting, I joined one co-creation team and we successfully submitted a Motivation Letter. For the first time, I was able to be a member of an international co-creation team and worked with a company from France. I was able to contribute my ideas and knowledge. This was really a valuable experience.”

9. Template for Evaluation of Solutions

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 3 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Solutions

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score	Evaluator
Deliverable quality	30 %	10	3		company
Business performance indicators / Technical performance indicators	60 %	10	6		company
Deadline compliance	10 %	10	1		points given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time
Total	100 %	30	10		

Scoring system with scores 0 to 10 (no decimals).

wherein:

0 - no effort made to fulfill any of listed aspects

1-2 - some aspects were not covered or all aspects were covered poorly

3-4 - all aspects covered but at least half of them poorly

5-6 - all aspects covered, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved

7-8 - all aspects clearly presented but could be improved

9-10 - all aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

- Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Decision: _____

Justification for the company to describe the deliverable quality (select one option)

- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of excellent and of very high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of acceptable quality.
- Reject the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of very low and unacceptable quality.

10. Questionnaire for Companies after completion of the Co-Creation Project

Questions for company representatives after submission of the final report

Satisfaction with following steps of the whole process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale** + option “I didn’t use it”)

- publishing the challenge
- registration on the platform
- user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)
- experience of the offline modules (support material and libraries) of the platform
- communication with the co-creation team
- adequateness of timeline between posting and start of challenge
- adequateness of timeline for solving the challenge
- revision of applications / motivation letters
- assisting co-creation team in carrying out the project
- preparation of deliverables, reports, etc.
- submission of deliverables, reports, etc.
- punctuality of deliverable submission

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Satisfaction with the Solution and work of the co-creation team (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**)

- Technical performance indicators:
 - Innovativeness: How do you estimate the innovative potential of the Solution?
 - Creativity: How do you evaluate the creativity of the Solution?
 - Improvement: How do you evaluate the performance of the Solution compared with your actual/previous solution (if not existent with a competitor’s solution)?
- Business performance indicators:
 - Market potential: How do you evaluate the market potential of the Solution?
 - Relevancy: How do you evaluate the relevance of the Solution?
- Quality
 - Soundness: How do you evaluate the soundness of the work of the co-creation team?

- Quality of work: How do you evaluate the quality of the work of the co-creation team?
- Satisfaction: How satisfied are you with the work of the co-creation team?
- Will you follow up on the Solution provided by the co-creation team within your company (No, definitely not – probably not – not decided yet – yes we will – yes, we already started)?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Have all requested deliverables been delivered by the co-creation team?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, the communication team will contact you for more information.

Testimonial: please provide a short testimonial, e.g. a letter or written statement of recommendation of something given or done as an expression of esteem, admiration, or gratitude. See two examples below:

“The company that issued the Challenge is active in the services sector. Due to a low number of employees and a busy schedule, it is a Challenge for them to find time to think out-of-the box. Within the INDUSAC co-creation project team, we not only got an opportunity to solve a real-life company problem and provide ideas for improved services but also got experience in international cooperation with fellow students and researchers. We would be happy to participate in similar initiatives in the future!”

“I learned about the INDUSAC at the university where I study. Then I checked the INDUSAC website and there were several Challenges from companies. Three Challenges were really interesting, I joined one co-creation team and we successfully submitted a Motivation Letter. For the first time I was able to be a member of an international co-creation team and worked with a company from France. I was able to contribute my ideas and knowledge. This was really a valuable experience.”

11. Statement of Non-disclosure of Information and Impartiality for INDUSAC Partners

STATEMENT ON NON-DISCLOSURE OF INFORMATION AND IMPARTIALITY

This statement pertains to procedures and activities carried out within the INDUSAC project.

This is to certify that I, the undersigned:

<Name and Surname>

<Home Address>

<Post Number and Town / City>

<State / Country>,

employed at:

<organisation>

member of the INDUSAC consortium

undertake that I shall not disclose confidential information (such as applications, work results, and personal data in connection to the INDUSAC piloting), acquired through activities within the INDUSAC Committee(s), through gathering and processing of data related to companies' and personal information regarding co-creation team applications, their work and their results, to unauthorised persons.

I hereby also confirm that I am not giving preferential treatment in regards to Motivation Letters Challenges / Solutions based on the applicant's professional or personal

connections with INDUSAC partners and that approval is based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters / Challenges / Solutions.

The obligations stated herein shall remain in force for a term of seven (7) years as from the date of signing hereof, and may be prolonged if the activities concerning the confidential data, as defined in this statement, continue after the expiration of this period.

This statement has been signed in 2 (two) identical paper copies, where one is for the signatory and one for the INDUSAC coordinator. The statement can be signed also electronically.

Place _____, date _____

Signature: _____

12. Call for Students and Researchers

Call for Students and Researchers

INDUSAC OPEN CALL FOR STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS

Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme

Call: A HUMAN-CENTRED AND ETHICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL AND INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES 2021 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01)

The call is managed by EU project INDUSAC under Horizon Europe programme. The Horizon Europe project INDUSAC, aims to financially support short-term (four to eight weeks) research collaborations between academia (students and researchers) and industry (companies), in solving company Challenges. Financial support to third parties (FSTP) is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams.

Expected outcome:

- 300 successful collaborations between industry and academia,
- Supported co-creation projects shall include at least 50% female representation overall (not on the individual co-creation project level).
- 60% of members of the co-creation teams must be from Widening Countries.
- Distribution of 900,000 EUR gross for FSTP to student members of the co-creation teams,

Students and researchers are invited to create co-creation teams and solve companies' Challenges within four to eight weeks.

Opening date: November 2023

Deadline model: single-stage, three cut-off dates

Deadline for submitting a Motivation Letter:

- 31.01.2024,
- 30.05.2024
- 30.10.2024

The Motivation Letter from a co-creation team is considered submitted once all co-creation team members confirm participation in the co-creation team and confirm the terms and conditions.

Although not mandatory, co-creation teams are encouraged to apply with a single strong Motivation Letter rather than multiple less-elaborated applications that may be rejected and thus cost them a valuable opportunity (since the maximum number of Motivation Letters throughout all three cut-off dates is three).

Eligibility

Eligible countries: In accordance with the [Horizon Europe Call](#), students and researchers in each co-creation team must come from EU Member States (Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Spain, Sweden), in particular Widening countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia; [source](#)) or Associated Countries (1. Albania, 2. Armenia, 3. Bosnia and Herzegovina, 4. Faroe Islands, 5. Georgia, 6. Iceland, 7. Israel, 8. Kosovo, 9. Moldova, 10. Montenegro, 11. North Macedonia, 12. Norway, 13. Serbia, 14. Tunisia, 15. Turkey, 16. Ukraine, 17. Morocco, 18. UK), **as indicated by their citizenship or residency.**

Eligibility for Students.

- Students must study at public universities during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed).
- An individual student will be able to participate in more than one co-creation team but be a candidate with a maximum of three Motivation Letters.

Eligibility for Researchers.

- Researchers must be employed at a public research organisation during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed).
- An individual researcher will be able to participate in more than one co-creation team but be a candidate with a maximum of three Motivation Letters.

Eligibility of Co-creation Teams

- The co-creation team must have at least three and up to six members.
- Co-creation team members must be from at least three different EU Member States or Associated Countries.
- The co-creation team has to be gender balanced (operationally, gender balance entails selecting at least two different gender options (Male, Female, Would rather not say)).
- Each co-creation team must include at least one student, ie. no co-creation team may comprise exclusively researchers.
- At least 60% of the members of the co-creation team must be from Widening Countries.

English is the official language of all INDUSAC documents using the Latin alphabet.

Budget: up to 1,000 EUR gross per student (lump sum), up to 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team wherein only students are eligible for funding; 900,000 EUR gross in total, for supporting 300 projects.

Application and implementation process

Step 1 - Registration

Prior to submitting Motivation Letters, students and researchers register (sign-up) (Annexes 1 and 2) on the INDUSAC platform (each student/researcher creates their own appropriate user account) and provides certain information.

Step 2 - Putting together a co-creation team

A student/researcher selects a Challenge. Once students/researchers have chosen a Challenge, they assemble a co-creation team. They may use the platform Slack (slack.com) or another communication channel of their choice. Each co-creation team (created on the platform) automatically gets an ID.

Students already registered on the INDUSAC platform can invite students not yet registered, to join a co-creation team via e-mail. Once a co-creation team has been assembled, members can create their own channels and discuss their ambitions, goals, and further details. In this chat, they also start preparing their Motivation Letter.

Step 3 - Motivation Letter submission

Once all co-creation team members are registered on the platform, a co-creation team can apply for a Challenge. The co-creation team must select the co-creation team leader, who submits a common Motivation Letter (ie. a single Motivation Letter per co-creation team) that is confirmed by all co-creation team members before the final submission.

After the closing of a cut-off date, no additions or changes to received Motivation Letters will be considered.

Motivation Letters (please refer to Annex 15 in this document) need to be submitted through the INDUSAC platform. Motivation Letters submitted by any other means will not be evaluated.

After the cut-off date, the company selects co-creation teams based on evaluation criteria and instructions for Motivation Letter (please refer to Annex 15 in this document).

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.
- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the 4-8 weeks time frame?

(5) TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

Table 4 : Evaluation criteria and scoring system for Motivation Letters

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring in points	Max scoring with weighting
Motivation	5 %	5	0,25
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5
Impact	30 %	5	1,5
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Excellence, 2 Impact, 3 Team and Resources, 4 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores.

Step 4 - Before the start of the co-creation project implementation

Students

Once the co-creation project is approved, each student member of the co-creation team fills out the Questionnaire (please refer to Annex 16 in this document), provides certain data (bank details, etc) and signs the FTSP declaration electronically.

Researchers

Once the co-creation project is approved, each research member of the co-creation team fills out the Questionnaire (please refer to Annex 16 in this document).

Step 5 - Implementation of co-creation projects

Students and researchers must solve companies' Challenges within four to eight weeks.

INDUSAC will provide the co-creation teams with a list of deliverables, methods and tools for the Challenge. In addition, the co-creation teams will be provided with a planned timeline / mentoring plan (to-do list) to complete the Challenge.

Throughout the process, each co-creation team should have the kick-off, at least one milestone meeting, and the feedback meeting with the company.

Monitoring of the Co-creation Projects by INDUSAC

Throughout the process, the company and the co-creation teams may be approached by the INDUSAC Mentoring Committee to discuss if they are progressing as planned and if they need any additional guidance.

On a more general level, a Monitoring Committee will be monitoring the performance of the co-creation projects on the INDUSAC platform and bring to the attention of the INDUSAC consortium any major irregularities or digressions from the work plan, so as to find rapid solutions.

Step 6 - Reporting

The results are reported in a Co-Creation Implementation Report through the INDUSAC platform (please refer to Annex 17 in this document) latest on 02.05.2024 (for the first cut-off date), 02.09.2024 (for the second cut-off date) or 01.02.2025 (for the third cut-off date).

The implementation report will include:

- Deliverables (according to a specific Challenge type) - uploaded on the platform by the co-creation team leader in the document section of the Challenge.
- Questionnaire “after” - filled out by each member of the co-creation team
 - Upskilling questionnaire
 - Testimonial
 - Short description of the project results
 - Inclusiveness statement
 - Compliance with the ethics requirement

which will be submitted via the platform.

Evaluation of Solutions

Each criterion will be scored from 0 to 10 and the weight of each one of these criteria, in the final score, will be as follows: Deliverable quality of submitted Solution (30% of the overall score); Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.

Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Timeline

- 31.01.2024 first cut-off date (deadline) for Motivation Letter submission
- 07.03.2024 deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (please refer to Annex 19 in this document), at which time the co-creation project begins
- 02.05.2024 deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams for the first cut-off date
- 15.06.2024 all students with approved reports receive funding (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised)
- 30.05.2024 second cut-off date (deadline) for Motivation Letter submission
- 08.07.2024 deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (please refer to Annex 19 in this document), at which time the co-creation project begins
- 02.09.2024 deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams for the second cut-off date
- 15.10.2024 all students with approved reports receive funding (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised).
- 30.10.2024 second cut-off date (deadline) for Motivation Letter submission
- 07.12.2024 deadline for students with approved Motivation Letters to sign a FSTP declaration (please refer to Annex 19 in this document) at which time the co-creation project begins
- 01.02.2025 deadline for submission of final reports by co-creation teams for the third cut-off date
- 14.3.2025 all students with approved reports receive funding (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised).

Financial support to third parties

Financial support to third parties (FSTP) based on a Lump sum is given solely to student members of the co-creation teams up to 1,000 EUR gross per student.

Students receive financial support to third parties after approval of the Implementation report on a Solution (as described in Step 6 - Reporting of this Call).

INDUSAC coordinator shall transfer the funds to students within thirty (30) days from the date of the approval of the implementation report (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised) on a Solution / final confirmation from the INDUSAC Evaluation Board.

Taxation

Payments will be done by the Jožef Stefan Institute (Slovenia). Since Jožef Stefan Institute will be transferring financial support to third parties (FSTP) to natural persons (individuals - students), Slovenian legislation and Slovenian accounting standards must be followed. The rate of taxation varies from country to country; in Slovenia it is 25%.

For students (Slovenian residents)

Slovenian residents provide their Slovenian Tax number. The taxation is 25%.

For students (Non residents of Slovenia)

- If students receive the FSTP as a one-time payment per year, they can provide their TAX number of country of residency. The taxation is 25%. If they wish, students can fill out a KIDO 4 form*** (request for exemption of tax on income, which students earn in the Republic of Slovenia, based on provisions of the treaty on avoidance of double taxation of income).
- If students receive multiple payments per year (i. e. they participate in several cut-off dates per year) they must obtain a Slovenian TAX number. The taxation is 25%. If they wish, students can fill out a KIDO 4 form*** (request for exemption of tax on income, which students earn in the Republic of Slovenia, based on provisions of the treaty on avoidance of double taxation of income).

*** KIDO 4 Form: If students (non-resident of Slovenia only) want to claim benefits in connection to the KIDO 4 form (request for exemption of tax on income, which students earn in the Republic of Slovenia, based on provisions of the treaty on avoidance of double taxation of income), they fill out the KIDO4 form, prepare necessary attachments, and send the whole documentation to Jožef Stefan Institute via email:

1. the KIDO 4 form (Republic of Slovenia State Tax Portal):
https://edavki.durs.si/OpenPortal/Dokumenti/kido_4.i.en.pdf;
2. instructions (Republic of Slovenia State Tax Portal):
https://edavki.durs.si/OpenPortal/Dokumenti/kido_4.n.en.pdf

Jožef Stefan Institute will submit the documentation to Financial administration of the Republic of Slovenia (FURS). FURS will review the documentation and issue a decision about reducing the tax rate or tax exemption in Slovenia. Based on the FURS's decision, Jožef Stefan Institute transfers the funds (FSTP) to students.

Terms and Conditions for students and researchers

Compliance with European Council Implementing Decision (on Hungarian entities).

The students/researchers confirm that they are not in conflict with the European Council Implementing Decision 2022/2506 in regards to funding Hungarian entities, which

stipulates that legal commitments must not be entered into with any public interest trusts established on the basis of the Hungarian Act IX of 2021 or any entity maintained by such a public interest trust. This applies as of 16.12.2022 for as long as the measures are in place. The students / researchers confirm that they are not associated with any of the affected entities listed on the Hungarian national legislation website (<https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2021-9-00-00>).

Confidentiality

For cases where students/researchers wish to share with the selected company their confidential information they are advised to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with the company before the start of the co-creation project.

INDUSAC partners who have access to the co-creation projects and co-creation results, have signed the Statement on Non-disclosure of Information and Impartiality (please refer to Annex 20 in this document) and all non-public and personal data will be treated in confidence.

Intellectual Property

Should the cooperation between student/researcher and the company give rise to any form of intellectual property (for example, a patent application), division of ownership of intellectual property rights (based on individual parties' contributions), the type of intellectual property, and management of said intellectual property, shall be defined in a separate agreement on joint inventions. The parties agree to the following provisions:

- On the basis of the undisputed fact that an invention presents a result of joint collaboration of student/researcher and the company and that student/researcher and the company were involved in the process of creation and development of the invention, the invention shall be considered as a joint invention of student/researcher and the company.
- Any intellectual property developed prior to the solving of a Challenge belongs to the party that developed it.
- Procedures such as registration and maintenance of the intellectual property shall be coordinated by the company.
- Students must follow the guidelines set by the company in regards to intellectual property disclosure and ownership; they may sign a statement waiving their economic intellectual property rights, by which they are exempt from any financial obligations towards protection of said intellectual property rights (such as, for example, preparation, registration / filing, processing, expansion, and maintenance fees); they may opt to retain authorship rights only, in which case they remain co-authors on the invention but receive no material benefits.

- Researchers must follow appropriate invention disclosure legislation, which may include disclosing the invention to their employer and subsequently transferring intellectual property rights to the employer.
- Regardless of status and intellectual property rights transfers, student/researcher retains the right to be listed as co-author on the invention.

The parties (company, student, researcher) agree that each party, individually or together with the remaining party, may use the invention for the purpose of its own research, without restrictions and without any obligation to remunerate the other party in any form or manner. The parties agree that the results of the co-creation project, except the INDUSAC requirements, will not be published, commercialised or otherwise allowed to be used by third parties without written agreement by all parties.

Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with:

- the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity).
- applicable EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Based on the Horizon Europe Ethic Self-Assessment guidance (European Commission, 2021) the co-creation team must ensure that the activities under the action do not include the following:

- human embryonic stem cells
- human embryos
- human foetal tissues/cells
- cause harm to the environment, animals, or plants
- military applications
- malevolent / criminal / terrorist abuse

Values

All parties must commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Conflict of interests

Students/researchers must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the co-creation project could be compromised for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').

By applying for the Call, students and researchers confirm that neither they nor their close family ties (spouse, domestic or non-domestic partner, child, sibling, parent etc.) are in business or scientific rivalry or professional hostility with the company behind the challenge they are submitting the Motivation Letter for.

Students further confirm that they are not receiving double financing for any of their activities within the INDUSAC project, ie. challenge solving activities within the co-creation team will not be funded from other sources except the INDUSAC financial support for third parties.

Applicants receiving financial support cannot be affiliated to any of the consortium partners, for example as consortium partner's board members or employees, with the exception of students employed for performing services unrelated to the challenge.

Disputes and exits

The parties (students, researchers, companies) agree that they will conclude in writing any amendments to any existing arrangements, and will endeavour to resolve any disputes regarding this arrangement in a peaceful manner. In the event that the parties cannot resolve the dispute individually, the INDUSAC coordinator shall mediate over the dispute. In the co-creation process, exit points of companies, students and researchers are foreseen only in case of Force Majeure.

Keeping records and supporting documents

The students/researchers acknowledge that they can substantiate the proper implementation of the action by records and other supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations.

The students/researchers can provide written proof, if required from INDUSAC partners, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Promotion. The members of the co-creation teams agree to provide statements / testimonials / experiences that can be published on the project website together with parts of the Challenge, through INDUSAC media and in project partners media.

Co-creation teams are given an option to have the INDUSAC communication team prepare a success story / a good practice story based on the co-creation team's project and results.

Communication, Dissemination And Visibility

Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the INDUSAC, communication activities of the parties (company, students, researcher) related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities or major results implemented under the INDUSAC must acknowledge INDUSAC and EU support and display the INDUSAC logo, European flag (emblem) and include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Graphic guide to use EU logo is available here:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains:

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] represents the author’s view only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency (European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)) do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”.

Supporting documentation:

- Registration Form for Students (please refer to Annex 13 in this document)
- Registration Form for Researchers (please refer to Annex 14 in this document)
- Motivation Letter Form (please refer to Annex 15 in this document)
- Skill level survey before the project (please refer to Annex 16 in this document)
- Template for co-creation Implementation Report (please refer to Annex 17 in this document)
- Declaration of Financial Support to Third Parties (please refer to Annex 19 in this document)
- Statement on Non-disclosure of Information and Impartiality for INDUSAC Partners (please refer to Annex 20 in this document)

- Template for Evaluation of Motivation Letters (please refer to Annex 21 in this document)
- Template for Evaluation of Solutions (please refer to Annex 22 in this document)

13. Registration Form for Students

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for students

Data needed when a student/researcher creates an account (**all the data is automatically inserted in the FSTP Declaration the students sign with INDUSAC**):

Mandatory fields marked with * are for the data that is visible to others after the login into the platform

- Name*
- Family name*
- Address
- Citizenship or residency (drop-down menu of the eligible countries) *
- Gender (tick: Male or Female or Would rather not say) *
- E-mail
- Month/year of study start – visible only to admin and for automatic verification of eligibility
- Foreseen month and year of study end (Students must study at public universities during the entire duration of the activity (from the co-creation team establishment until one month after the final report of the co-creation team is confirmed) – visible only to admin and for automatic verification of eligibility
- Name of the public university where you study *
- Country of the university *
- Website of the university
- Mark your area of study:
 - Chemistry (CHE)
 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC)
 - Economic Sciences (ECO)
 - Information Science and Engineering (ENG)
 - Environment and Geosciences (ENV)
 - Life Sciences (LIF)
 - Mathematics (MAT)
 - Physics (PHY)
- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers.
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (personal data to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published).

14. Registration Form for Researchers

REGISTRATION FORM ON THE PLATFORM for researchers

Marked with * for the data that is visible to others after the login into the platform

- Name *
- Family name *
- Citizenship or residency (drop-down menu of the eligible countries)*
- Gender (tick Male or Female or Would rather not say) *
- E-mail (organisation email is mandatory)
- Name of the public research organisation where you work *
- Website of their employer *
- Mark your area of research:
 - Chemistry (CHE)
 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC)
 - Economic Sciences (ECO)
 - Information Science and Engineering (ENG)
 - Environment and Geosciences (ENV)
 - Life Sciences (LIF)
 - Mathematics (MAT)
 - Physics (PHY)

- Tick the box: I confirm that the information provided in the registration process is complete, reliable and true.
- Tick the box: we accept all Terms and Conditions as set out in the Call for Students and Researchers.
- Tick the box: I give my permission to preserve and share information given in this questionnaire strictly for the purposes of the INDUSAC project (personal data to be shared strictly within the INDUSAC consortium and non-personal data to be used for the purposes of statistical analyses, the results of which may be published).

15. Motivation Letter Form

Challenge title

Attachments

Drag and drop your files here –

Add pictures and other visuals to increase the description of your solution proposal

*Please upload your resume and, if needed, further documents concerning your idea for a solution.
Possible formats: PDF, JPG, DOC, AVI, MPG4, XLS*

Team ID

Please be aware that the motivation will only be processed after submission, if all linked team members confirm their participation. An automated e-mail will be sent to every team member after you submit the motivation.

Describe your team motivation

Describe your team motivation in your own words. You should include why you as a team are most suitable to find a great solution for this challenge in collaboration with the industry partner. You can use this field to give a quick introduction to all the team members and let everybody state their personal motivation for this challenge. The conclusion should answer why you as a team are well prepared to solve this challenge.

Example Conclusion: We as a team will find a great solution together since we not only come from different countries but we also study three very different degrees which will help us to think out of the box. Jane studies mechanical engineering and has a lot of experience with building physical prototypes. Tim is in his third year of an architecture bachelor's. He knows a lot about different materials, and has also been building prototypes since his first semester. Melanie studies corporate law and works in her free time for an NGO. We see ourselves as qualified not only to find an innovative solution but also to visualize it through a prototype. Furthermore, we will focus on finding a sustainable and durable solution that can be used in all countries. To make sure it fits with the different countries' regulations, Melanie uses her knowledge from a European corporate law class.

How will you address the following aspects? (you may respond to all the criteria if possible) (up to 5000 characters):

Excellence

How will your team reach an excellent solution for this challenge? Why is your team one that can propose a solution that might become a real innovation?

Impact

Why do you believe your team will find a solution that can be successful on the market? To what level will your solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? You may also describe what you already found out about the companies' competition and how you are trying to get to a differentiated solution. Do you already have ideas about how a solution to this challenge might not only solve the challenge but tackle a respective structural problem? How important will the project in your opinion be for the company? Will the solution be implementable also in other sectors?

Team & Resources

Demonstrate your transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, your ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and your capacity to carry through your ideas and understand the dynamics of the market you are trying to tap into. Do you have specific resources that qualify you as a team specifically to find an excellent solution? Do you plan a visit to the companies' premises within the duration of the project? Do you plan any other travel (national or international; e.g., visiting a library, visiting a teammate, visiting a prototyping centre etc.)? How much time (hours/team member) do you plan to invest in this project?

Transversal criteria

Do you have ideas to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', "Inclusiveness" or 'Social Impact' within your way to a solution for the challenge? If yes you may describe here how or why you are planning to do so.

Idea for solution (optional)

Optional: If you already have an idea for a solution for this challenge, please briefly describe it here. Note: filling this field is optional (up to 5000 characters)

Describe the idea you have for solving this challenge as clearly as you can. It might include which technology you plan on using, procedures you believe solve the challenge, services or other details

you came already up with in your team. If applicable please make sure you are not disclosing any confidential information.

About you

16. Skill Level Survey for Students / Researchers before the Project

Questions for co-creation team members upon receiving info about positive selection (before the start of the co-creation project):

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results-oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working within international teams
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills would you like to develop/improve:
 - Communication skills
 - Negotiation
 - Results-oriented thinking
 - Responsibility
 - Creativity
 - Planning skills
 - Analytical thinking
 - Critical thinking
 - Conflict management
 - Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
 - Common goal definition
 - Time management and effective planning
 - Leadership

- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Understanding for international colleagues
- English

Yes/no questions

Are you familiar with the following methods:

- SWOT analysis
- Persona Method
- Utility analysis
- Trend analysis
- Scenario analysis
- Cost-benefit analyses
- Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix
- White spot analysis
- Creating marketing strategies
- Value proposition analysis
- Developing a business plan
- Preparation of business model canvas
- Building a Product Service System
- Detecting ideas
- Empathy map
- Kano-method
- Building prototypes
- Simulation model
- Virtual prototype
- Target group analysis

17. Template for Co-Creation Implementation Report

To be filled out by each member of the co-creation team.

Co-Creation Implementation Report	
Title of the Challenge	
Team Leader	
Team Member	
Team Member	
Start of project	(date)
End of project	(date)
<p>Short description of the project results. Please provide a short description of the project results and a short description of your personal contribution (five sentences total). Note that the description will be published on the INDUSAC website and on the EU platform so please don't include classified information.</p>	
<p>List of Deliverables prepared and uploaded on the platform</p>	
<p>Inclusiveness statement (explain in a few sentences how your solution is inclusive, ie. not excluding any groups of individuals in terms of gender, race, nationality, etc.)</p>	
Upskilling, clarity and satisfaction questionnaire	(see below***)

Testimonial: please provide a short testimonial, e.g. a letter or written statement of recommendation of something given or done as an expression of esteem, admiration, or gratitude. See two examples below:

“The company that issued the Challenge is active in the services sector. Due to a low number of employees and a busy schedule, it is a Challenge for them to find time to think out-of-the box. Within the INDUSAC co-creation project team, we not only got an opportunity to solve a real-life company problem and provide ideas for improved services but also got experience in international cooperation with fellow students and researchers. We would be happy to participate in similar initiatives in the future!”

“I learned about the INDUSAC at the university where I study. Then I checked the INDUSAC website and there were several Challenges from companies. Three Challenges were really interesting, I joined one co-creation team and we successfully submitted a Motivation Letter. For the first time I was able to be a member of an international co-creation team and worked with a company from France. I was able to contribute my ideas and knowledge. This was really a valuable experience.”

18. Questionnaire for Students/Researchers after Completion of the Co-creation Project

The purpose of the questionnaire is to evaluate the level of upskilling achieved during the co-creation project.

Questions for students/researchers after submission of the final report

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results-oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working within international teams
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills were significantly developed / improved through the co-creation team project:
 - Communication skills
 - Negotiation
 - Results-oriented thinking
 - Responsibility
 - Creativity
 - Planning skills
 - Analytical thinking
 - Critical thinking
 - Conflict management
 - Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
 - Common goal definition
 - Time management and effective planning

- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working within international teams
- English

Yes/no questions

Are you familiar with the following methods:

- SWOT analysis
- Persona Method
- Utility analysis
- Trend analysis
- Scenario analysis
- Cost-benefit analyses
- Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix
- White spot analysis
- Creating marketing strategies
- Value proposition analysis
- Developing a business plan
- Preparation of business model canvas
- Building a Product Service System
- Detecting ideas
- Empathy map
- Kano-method
- Building prototypes
- Simulation model
- Virtual prototype
- Target group analysis

Please, evaluate your experience in terms of clarity and satisfaction with the process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**):

Topic	clarity of the process	satisfaction
finding the detailed information about the Challenge		
user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)		
method assistance through explanations and templates		
assistance through the proposed process and milestones		
registration on the platform		
creation of a team		
timeline of challenge application process		
timeline for solving the challenge		
submission of application / Motivation Letter		
working in a team - with other students / researchers		
working in a team - with company		
preparation of deliverables (Solution, reports, etc.)		
submission of deliverables (Solution, reports, etc.)		
(students only) financial transaction process		

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Collaboration

How often did you meet the company representative?

- 1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more often

Which communication channel did you use?

- 1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar Messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

How often did you meet with your team members?

- 1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more often

Which communication channel did you use?

- 1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar Messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

Did you benefit from working in a multicultural team?

- 1) Not at all 2) a bit 3) neutral 4) Yes I did 5) Yes a lot

Rate the level of agreement or disagreement with each statement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents "Strongly Disagree" and 5 represents "Strongly Agree."

- The co-creation mechanism encouraged active participation and engagement from all participants.
- The co-creation process encouraged collaboration and co-learning among the participants.
- The co-creation process incorporated customer research and insights to understand the end-users' needs and preferences.
- The co-creation process fostered interdisciplinary collaboration, integrating perspectives from social sciences and humanities to other disciplines.
- We, as a team, were encouraged to explore ethical considerations and social impact when generating ideas during the co-creation process.
- I was able to participate equally in the decision-making process.
- The co-creation process resulted in solutions that specifically addressed gender-related issues or considerations.
- Overall, the co-creation process successfully prioritised the human aspect (Inclusivity, Gender dimension, Interdisciplinarity, User Perspective, Collaboration, Iterative Feedback, Ethical Considerations) and created a meaningful and inclusive environment.

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Please, evaluate your current level of agreement with the following statements (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale**) + option "I didn't use it":

- Help desk assistance (e.g. value of support received) was adequate.
- It is likely you would recommend participation in such a program to other peers
- Challenges were diverse enough and you were able to find an interesting one fast and start the co-creation process
- The Challenges were well described.
- Companies' expectations were reasonable.
- You are satisfied with the results that your co-creation team submitted,
- You benefited from working in an international environment.

Open questions:

- Appropriateness of funding: did you find funding appropriate, high enough? Were you able to cover all your costs? Considering actual costs and given rational consideration, do you feel that the funding received would be sufficient for supporting more than one co-creation project?
- What is the main reason you applied to INDUSAC open calls (money, connections to students and/or companies/researchers, international experiences, new skills etc.)?
- How would you rate your experience with the provided method recommendations and explanations, templates, process and milestone recommendations?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, the communication team will contact you for more information.

19. INDUSAC Declaration of Financial Support to Third Parties

INDUSAC DECLARATION on Financial Support to Third Parties

We, the undersigned,

Co-creation Team member 1 (student)

Name
Family name
Address
Residency
Tax number from the country of residency
Gender
E-mail
Month/year of study start
Name of public university where you study
Country of the university
Bank Details
Bank Name and Address
Transaction Account
IBAN
SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 2 (student)

Name
Family name
Address
Residency
Tax number from the country of residency
Gender
E-mail
Month / year of study start
Name of public university where you study
Country of the university
Bank Details
Bank Name and Address
Transaction Account

IBAN
SWIFT Code of Bank

Co-creation Team member 3 (student)

Name
Family name
Address
Residency
Tax number from the country of residency
Gender
E-mail
Month/year of study start
Name of public university where you study
Country of the university
Bank Details
Bank Name and Address
Transaction Account
IBAN
SWIFT Code of Bank

additional Co-creation Team members (students)

xx
xx
xx

hereby declare that:

- we have established a cooperation, within the Horizon Europe INDUSAC project, with the INDUSAC project coordinator, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, with the intention of solving a Challenge entitled <Title of the Challenge> issued by a company <company name> within a time frame of four to eight weeks;
- we comprise a co-creation team represented by a co-creation team leader and at least two additional student/researchers, wherein all members of the co-creation team share equal treatment and responsibilities;
- the co-creation team, in addition to the listed students, comprises the following researchers as well:
_____;
- we accept the terms and conditions of the Call for Students and Researchers published on the INDUSAC website
- we accept the financial support to third parties, provided by the INDUSAC project coordinator, and in the amount of up to 3,000 EUR gross per co-creation team and up to 1,000 EUR gross per individual student, based on financial support eligibility terms listed in the Call for Students and Researchers

The declaration shall enter into force on the date on which it is signed by all parties.

The declaration must be signed digitally.

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 1 (student)

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 2 (student)

Place, date _____

Name of co-creation Team Member 3 (student)

Statement of Non-Disclosure of Information and Impartiality for INDUSAC Partners

20. Statement of Non-Disclosure of Information and Impartiality for INDUSAC Partners

STATEMENT ON NON-DISCLOSURE OF INFORMATION AND IMPARTIALITY

This statement pertains to procedures and activities carried out within the INDUSAC project.

This is to certify that I, the undersigned:

<Name and Surname>

<Home Address>

<Post Number and Town / City>

<State / Country>,

employed at:

<organisation>

member of the INDUSAC consortium

undertake that I shall not disclose confidential information (such as applications, work results, and personal data in connection to the INDUSAC piloting), acquired through activities within the INDUSAC Committee(s), through gathering and processing of data related to companies' and personal information regarding co-creation team applications, their work and their results, to unauthorised persons.

I hereby also confirm that I am not giving preferential treatment in regards to Motivation Letters Challenges / Solutions based on the applicant's professional or personal connections with INDUSAC partners and that approval is based solely on the quality of the Motivation Letters / Challenges / Solutions.

The obligations stated herein shall remain in force for a term of seven (7) years as from the date of signing hereof, and may be prolonged if the activities concerning the confidential data, as defined in this statement, continue after the expiration of this period.

This statement has been signed in two (2) identical paper copies, where one is for the signatory and one for the INDUSAC coordinator. The statement can also be signed electronically.

Place _____, date _____

Signature: _____

21. Template for Evaluation: Motivation Letters

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 5 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Motivation Letters

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score
Team's motivation	5 %	5	0,25	
Excellence	30 %	5	1,5	
Impact	30 %	5	1,5	
Team and resources	30 %	5	1,5	
Transversal criteria	5 %	5	0,25	
Total	100 %	25	5	

Scoring system with scores 0 to 5 (no decimals).

wherein:

- 0 - Motivation Letter makes no effort to fulfill any of listed aspects
- 1 - Motivation Letter does not address all aspects or covers all aspects poorly
- 2 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects but at least half of them poorly
- 3 - Motivation Letter covers all aspects, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved
- 4 - All aspects clearly presented but could be improved
- 5 - All aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

Motivation Letters that receive a score 0 in one or more criteria (1 Motivation, 2 Excellence, 3 Impact, 4 Team and Resources, 5 Transversal criteria) will be automatically rejected.

Accepted Motivation Letters need to receive all together at least 50% of available scores.

Decision (accept / reject): _____

Justification in case of rejection (select one or more options)

- The teams' motivation is not convincing enough and several parts are poorly addressed.
- Excellence: The foreseen approach, the credibility of the proposed methodology, the efficiency and quality of the proposed work are not convincing.
- Impact: The motivation letter does not provide information relevant or credible enough to consider that the team will be able to provide a differentiated or innovative solution that can be successful on the market or relevant for the company.
- Team and resources: One or several of the required aspects, within the team and resources, to develop a solution in a four to eight weeks time frame are missing.
- Transversal criteria: The ideas on how to include transversal criteria within the teams' way to a solution for the challenge are poorly considered.

Evaluation criteria for evaluating the Motivation Letters (from co-creation teams):

(1). TEAM'S MOTIVATION (5%)

- Personal motivation: reflection of a team's enthusiasm for taking on the challenge.
- Did the team introduce the team members? (yes/no)
- Do their strengths and abilities adequately explain the reason why they are suitable? (yes/ no)
- Will they be able to work together as a team? Do they already have team cohesion?

(2). EXCELLENCE (30%):

- Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology, according to the expectations of companies.
- Are the efficiency and quality of work related to the challenge well explained?

(3). IMPACT (30%):

- Do you believe the co-creation team will find a solution that can be successful on the market?
- To what level will the potential solution be innovative in regards to the existing solutions on the market (incremental improvement, radical improvement, breakthrough innovation, ...)? Focus on the creativity of how the team predicted their future success and not on a potential solution they might have proposed.
- Has a co-creation team already found out about the companies' competition and how they will try to get to a differentiated solution?
- How important will the project be for the company and how well did the team foresee the impact?

(4). TEAM AND RESOURCES (30%):

- Transversal, entrepreneurial and leadership skills, technical expertise, co-creation teams' ability to take a concept from ideas to market, and their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into.

- Does the team have specific resources that qualify them as a team specifically to find an excellent solution?
- Is the foreseen time consumption (hours/team member) for the co-creation project sensibly aligned with the project structure, and fitting within the four to eight weeks time frame?

(5) TRANSVERSAL CRITERIA (5%):

- Does a co-creation team have ideas on how to include 'Environment and low carbon economy contribution', 'Equal Opportunities, Gender balance & Diversity', 'Inclusiveness' or 'Social Impact' within their way to a solution for the challenge?

22. Template for Evaluation of Solutions

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Table 6 : Criteria and scoring system for evaluating Solutions

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score	Evaluator
Deliverable quality	30 %	10	3		company
Business performance indicators / Technical performance indicators	60 %	10	6		company
Deadline compliance	10 %	10	1		points given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time
Total	100 %	30	10		

Scoring system with scores 0 to 10 (no decimals).

wherein:

0 - no effort made to fulfill any of listed aspects

1-2 - some aspects were not covered or all aspects were covered poorly

3-4 - all aspects covered but at least half of them poorly

5-6 - all aspects covered, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved

7-8 - all aspects clearly presented but could be improved

9-10 - all aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

- Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Decision: _____

Justification for the company to describe the deliverable quality (select one option)

- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of excellent and of very high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of acceptable quality.
- Reject the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of very low and unacceptable quality.

III. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable represents an overview of the documentation necessary to carry out the co-creation process, from registering on the INDUSAC platform to the documents needed after the co-creation project has finished. As such, it serves as an abridged version of the project's methodology and a quick-reference manual of the INDUSAC project.

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